

The Mapping and Planetary Spatial Infrastructure Team (MAPSIT)

Terms of Reference

Version June 2026

Purpose

The acquisition, organization, and analysis of planetary spatial data, including images, cartographic products, and geologic maps are critical for linking science investigation and exploration planning for all solid bodies in the Solar System.

The Mapping and Planetary Spatial Infrastructure Team (MAPSIT) is a community-based interdisciplinary forum for the discussion, analysis, and representation of matters concerning the creation and development of planetary geographic information, spatially-registered data, and cartographic products; a program of sustained planetary geologic mapping; and the tools and training necessary for these capabilities.

The MAPSIT mission is to advance U.S. objectives in space achievement by ensuring that planetary spatial data are usable for any conceivable purpose, now and in the future, by the scientific and engineering communities.

Community

Participation in MAPSIT activities is open to all members of the planetary science and exploration community, particularly those scientists, engineers, technologists, and other professionals—in academia, government, or the commercial sector—who are interested in planetary spatial data infrastructure. International participation is welcome.

Activities

To execute its mission, MAPSIT will:

- 1) Generate findings for the community concerning the scientific rationale, objectives, technology, and long range strategic priorities for effective acquisition and processing of planetary spatial data, integration of image datasets, geospatial software development, and geologic mapping and other cartographic programs;
- 2) Help ensure that the best geospatial data acquisition, processing and analysis, geologic mapping and cartographic standards, and planetary nomenclature are developed for, and maintained in, present and future NASA flight missions and research activities;

- 3) Encourage the development of standards to assess the accuracy and precision required for cartographic and geographic information systems technologies and products;
- 4) Help develop and support planetary spatial data infrastructures to effectively acquire, process, integrate, and distribute planetary data to the community so that products “just work” for users;
- 5) Encourage the development of tools, data products, and services, that will help ensure the best technologies can be applied to data processing, use, storage and visualization of planetary spatial data;
- 6) Facilitate the generation of geospatial data products and programmatic capabilities required for the planning of U.S. robotic precursor missions and human exploration of the Solar System, and enable a broad continuum of exploration activities, which include (but are not limited to) science analysis of planetary surfaces, the identification of safe landing sites, sampling locations, hazard assessment, and the geospatial characterization of planetary surfaces and in-situ resources;
- 7) Encourage training of personnel in the community for the use and improvement of spatial data-related tools, software, and products;
- 8) Help coordinate and enable the co-registration of datasets from U.S. missions;
- 9) Help coordinate and enable the co-registration of datasets from international missions with those from U.S. missions;
- 10) Support NASA and the USGS as needed in developing, fostering, and maintaining critical U.S. geospatial, cartographic, and geologic mapping capabilities;
- 11) Provide a regular forum for broad discussion related to planetary spatial data infrastructure and emerging needs, serving as a conduit for community input into planetary exploration activities and planning;
- 12) Maintain a close connection with – and facilitate communication among – NASA, any NASA advisory groups, Federal mapping agencies, allied space agencies, relevant international coordination entities (e.g., the International Astronomical Union) on the topics of planetary spatial data, and the planetary science community; and
- 13) Communicate findings and assessments to the planetary science community and stakeholders. This may include reports or findings in response to requests from the relevant NASA mission directorates, including Science Mission Directorate (SMD), Human Spaceflight Mission Directorate (HSMD), and the Research and Technology Mission Directorate (RTMD), other agencies, or relevant advisory groups. MAPSIT prefers to publish all findings and reports publicly by posting them online, such as our webpage or through a document repository with a DOI link.

Together, these actions will help ensure that the planetary science community can widely leverage planetary geospatial data and products to make ongoing research discoveries that advance Solar System research goals.

Organization

The MAPSIT Steering Committee consists of the Chair, the Vice-Chair, the Past Chair, and up to 15 at-large representatives from the planetary science and exploration communities. *Ex Officio* members of the Steering Committee can include the director of the USGS Astrogeology Science Center, NASA liaisons, and the Planetary Data System Chief Scientist. All *Ex Officio* members are non-voting members.

The Chair of MAPSIT is drawn from the U.S. planetary science community and is appointed for a term of three years. The incoming Chair is appointed by the outgoing Chair.

The Vice-Chair is also drawn from the U.S. planetary science community and is appointed for a term of up to three years. The Vice-Chair is appointed by the Chair by seeking nominations from the Steering Committee and/or the broader community. The Chair may choose to appoint the Vice-Chair (a route to preserve knowledge continuity) to be the incoming Chair, if amenable to both parties, or by seeking nominations from the Steering Committee and/or through an open call. The Chair and Vice-Chair should not have any significant conflicts of interest that would hinder their unbiased service to the community. The Steering Committee by majority vote has the authority to determine what qualifies as a significant conflict of interest.

The Past Chair may choose to continue to serve on the Steering Committee as a regular at-large member for up to three additional years.

Nominations for all other at-large Steering Committee are solicited through an open call to the community, and appointments are made by the MAPSIT Chair, in consultation with the Steering Committee. The Steering Committee is constituted to achieve a functional balance and diversity from members of the planetary geospatial community. The nominal term for Steering Committee members is three years. Terms may be renewed at the discretion of the Chair. Appointments may be terminated at any time by mutual agreement or for significant reasons such as due to a member's lack of availability for an extended period, disrespectful behavior, or a conflict of interest.

All Steering Committee members are expected to contribute to MAPSIT activities through discussions, drafting/writing, presentations, website and other communications, organizational activities, telecons, and meetings to the fullest extent possible. A typical time commitment depends on the current activities of the committee, ranging from a few hours a month to a week during a month (e.g., in support of a MAPSIT community meeting or specific action team report). If a Steering Committee member has a conflict of interest with a particular topic or finding, it is expected that they will declare a conflict and recuse themselves from the related

activities.

The MAPSIT Chair provides final approval, prioritization, and scheduling of MAPSIT activities after consultation with the MAPSIT Steering Committee. The Chair is responsible for reporting and posting findings (as described above), but may delegate to the Vice-Chair or other Steering Committee members. Prior to posting, MAPSIT reports and findings will be reviewed by the MAPSIT Steering Committee, typically after discussion in an open MAPSIT forum.

The MAPSIT Steering Committee may organize ad hoc or standing subcommittees to address specific issues, with membership open to community-based experts upon invitation from the Steering Committee after an open call. Standing subcommittees must be chaired by a member of the Steering Committee. Ad hoc subcommittees may be chaired by experts from outside of MAPSIT upon invitation from the Steering Committee. These sub-groups report their findings to the Steering Committee and the full community. The MAPSIT chair has final approval of any subcommittee reports or findings to be posted under the MAPSIT umbrella.

The MAPSIT Steering Committee meets approximately once per month by telecon to discuss critical issues and plan for community meetings. The full MAPSIT community meets at least once per year (e.g., a virtual town hall or adjacent to a relevant conference). The MAPSIT Chair and Steering Committee set and announce the regular annual meeting schedule and public meeting agendas.

Last Updated by the MAPSIT Steering Committee, on 9 June 2026.